

Figure S9. Saliva proteins differentially expressed 1 and 2 h after OFC

Colored areas in the volcano plots show the differentially expressed proteins upregulated and downregulated among (A) 1 h after OFC, (B) 2 h after OFC relative to the time before OFC in the OFC-positive group as well as (C) 1 h after OFC and (D) 2 h after OFC relative to the time before OFC in the OFC-negative group. Proteome analysis of serum samples was performed using 6 biological replicates for the OFC-positive group and 11 biological replicates for the OFC-negative group.